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Effect of Gibberellic Acid on Germination, Vegetative and Reproductive Characters of Different Varieties of Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.)

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Abstract

The research was carried out to evaluate the effect of Gibberellic acid (GA3) seed treatment on vegetative and reproductive characteristics of different varieties of tomato in Dhading, Nepal in 2022. The experiment was carried out in two factorial Randomized complete block designs using three replications and eight treatments. Four levels of GA3 (0, 250, 500 and 750 ppm) with two locally popular varieties of tomato (Dalila and Platinum F1) were used as treatments. The results revealed that GA3 seed treatment at various levels was significant for both varieties on most of the parameters. GA3 seed treatment at 750 ppm resulted in shorter days to 50% germination (7.74), increase in plant height at transplanting (16.33 cm), plant height at 15 (40.77cm), 30 (86.67cm), and 45 (161.67cm) days after transplanting for Dalila variety whereas GA3 seed treatment at 500 ppm resulted in shorter days to 50% germination (8.06), increased plant height at transplanting (14.27cm), plant height at 15 (34.33cm), 30 (76.33cm), and 45 (142.67cm) days after transplanting for Platinum F1 variety. The later stage characters were only influenced by varietal differences where the Dalila variety was superior with a higher number of flowers per plant at 30 (5.50) and 45 (11.67) DAT and several fruits per plant (5.41) at 45 DAT. So, based on the current research, 750 ppm GA3 seed treatment for Dalila and 500 ppm seed treatment for Platinum F1 resulted in maximum vegetative growth whereas the Dalila F1 variety was superior to the Platinum F1 variety for both vegetative and reproductive characteristics on treated as well as untreated plots.

Keywords: Tomato, Nepal, Gibberellic Acid (GA3), Dalila, Platinum F1

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) is an annual, herbaceous annual plant. It is universally treated as protective food for being extensively grown worldwide, ranking second in importance to potatoes. It is one of the most popular vegetable crops grown worldwide and is widely consumed as a fresh and processed product (Vardhini & Ramrao, 2001) with 2n=24 chromosomes belonging to the Solanaceae family. It originated in the western coastal plain of South America (Thompson & Kelly, 1957) and was spread to other parts of the world in the 16th century. The tomato became popular in Nepal mostly in the last four to five decades.

Tomato is a self-pollinated crop having a tap root system. Depending upon the growth habit, tomato plants can be categorized into two types viz. determinate and indeterminate types. In the case of determinate type, the plant attains its full vegetative growth before flowering initiation and the plant terminates in a flower bud which is also called the 'self-topping' or 'self-pruning' type. On the other hand, the indeterminate type of tomato is tall as the terminal portion of the stems continues to grow and flower is produced at every third internode. The red

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colour of tomato is due to lycopene pigment, whereas yellow and orange are due to carotene and polyycopene pigments, respectively. Tomato is also known as poor man's orange.

It is commercially cultivated in the country. The production process is labour-intensive and wage alone costs more than half of the production cost. The production area is increasing in the country as consumption and demand for tomatoes are increasing. The farmers have been following both seasonal and off-seasonal production to counter the demand throughout the year. The market price and demand for tomatoes also fluctuate with the season and location of the country. The tomato is produced seasonally in the summer in the hills which is From May to September when it is off-season for Terai. Unlike Hills tomatoes can be produced in the Terai in winter which is from November to March when it's too cold in Hills.

As per the Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture, 2019/20 the area, production and productivity of tomatoes in Nepal is estimated to be 21747 ha, 413761 MT and 19.03 MT/ha, respectively whereas in Dhading it is being cultivated in 776 ha with the average productivity of 18.00 MT/ha (MOALD, 2021).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Site and Soil Characteristics

The experiment was conducted on a Farmer's field at Siddhalek-3, Dhading district in Bagmati province of Nepal. The climate of the location was subtropical with temperatures quite hotter than the hilly regions and situated at 27° 48' 16" N and 84° 52' 32" E with an elevation of around 400M above sea level.

Map of Nepal showing Dhading district

Map of Dhading showing research location

Figure: Map of Nepal Showing Study Area

The soil of the experimental site was sandy soil with a low level of organic matter (1.81%), low available Nitrogen (0.09%), Low availability of Phosphorus (18.30 kg/ha) and medium potassium content (273.6 kg/ha) with normal or neutral pH of 7.3.

Planting materials

The seed of two locally popular varieties i.e., Platinum F1 and Dalila were used as planting materials.

Date of sowing

The nursery was prepared by the first week of March and seedling transplantation was taken place by the first week of April.

Spacing

The geometry of the crop was 60*40cm the size of the plot was 2.4*2.4M with four rows and six plants per row counting a total of 24 plants per plot.

Design of the experiment

The experimental design was a factorial Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) which is designed for homogeneous field conditions as present in the selected field. There were four different doses of seed treatment of GA3 for two varieties. Combining a total of eight treatments each treatment was replicated thrice.

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Table 1: List of Variety and application doses

Variety	GA3 Dose (ppm)	Treatments
Dalila(V1)	0 (Control)	T ₁
	250	T ₂
	500	T ₃
	750	T ₄
Platinum(V2)	0 (Control)	T ₅
	250	T ₆
	500	T ₇
	750	T ₈

Figure: Layout of field

Table 2: Details of experimental design used in the study site at, Dhading, Nepal, 2022

S. N	Particular	Trial details
1.	Design	Two factorial RCBD
2.	Replication (Blocks)	3
3.	Treatments	8
4.	Plot Size	2.4×2.4 m ²
5.	Spacing between replication	0.6m
6.	Spacing between plots within the replication	0.4m
7.	Total no. of plots	24
8.	No. of plants per plot	24 (4rows and 6 columns)
9.	Total no. of plants	576
10.	Spacing	60×40 cm ²
11.	Sample	5 random central plants

Seed Treatment

The seeds of both varieties i.e., Platinum F1 and Dalila were treated 24 hr before sowing. Four solutions of GA3 Water were made namely 0ppm (control), 250ppm, 500ppm and 750 ppm. A seed lot of 100 seeds of each variety was wrapped in a paper towel and dipped into each solution for 24 hr. Every treatment was replicated thrice combining a total of 300 seeds of a variety dipped in a single concentration. So, a total of 1200 seeds of Platinum F1 and the same no. of Dalila, seeds were treated.

The ppm was calculated by using the following formula

$$\text{Parts per million(ppm)} = \frac{\text{Weight of solute(mg)}}{\text{Volume of solvent (Litres)}}$$

For control treatments, the seeds were soaked in distilled water.

Nursery Preparation

The treated seeds were sown on polythene plant bags. The FYM, soil and sand mixture at a 1:1:2 ratio was made and filled in pots. On each bag, a single seed was sown and the emerged seedlings were sown to the main field.

Land Preparation

For good growth and development of Tomato plants, the field condition during and before transplanting has a pivotal role. So, intensive preparation of land during transplanting is required for successful plant growth. About 3-4 deep ploughing followed by harrowing and levelling was done to make soil free from weeds and large soil clods. The plants were sown on raised plots.

Planting

The seedlings of 4 weeks of age (healthy, well grown, free of disease and stress) were transplanted to the main field. Transplanting was done followed by moderate watering of the field.

Manuring and fertilization

The Manuring and fertilizer application was done based on soil testing. The soil testing was done with the technical aid of the Soil and Fertilizer Testing Laboratory, Hetauda, Nepal.

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All the fertilizers were applied during land preparation as basal dose except Urea, which was applied on basal as well as split doses i.e., ½ dose during planting and the remaining ½ was applied equally at 30 and 45 DAT.

Irrigation

The irrigation was applied on plots by sprinkler and sometimes by flooding. The frequency of irrigation was variable concerning the depth of previous application, environment temperature and seasonal rainfall. In case of flooding the water is applied up to 2/3rd height of the plot.

Intercultural practices

Intercultural practices like earthing up and weeding were performed at 15,30 and 45 DAT. Weeding was also performed in between these dates when necessary.

Sampling Technique

100 seeds were sown in each plot and then randomly selected plants were transplanted to the main field. Five random plants in each plot before and after transplanting were studied in the successive stages of crop growth. The measurements for seedling stages were taken at every seven days intervals from sowing.

RESULTS

Days to 50% emergence

The days to 50% emergence were significantly influenced by different doses of Hormone, Varietal differences as well and Interaction between the two. The average days for 50% emergence were decreased with increasing the concentration up to 500 ppm ranging from 8.34 days at 500 ppm to 9.91 days at 0 ppm. The days were significantly lower for Dalila variety i.e., 8.81 days as compared to 9.91 days of Platinum F1. The Hormone: Variety interaction also influenced the results significantly (Table 3).

The concentration of hormone at 500 ppm and 750 ppm resulted in the least days to 50% emergence which were statistically similar i.e., 8.34 and 8.45 days respectively followed by 9.29 days at 250 ppm which was significantly better than 9.91 days at control treatment.

The Hormone: Variety interaction influenced the days to 50% emergence as the Dalila at 500 ppm has shown the best effect i.e., 7.75 days followed by Platinum F1 at 500 ppm which resulted in 50% emergence at 8.06 days. The longest time taken was 10.06 days by Platinum F1 seed at control treatment followed by Dalila: Control which resulted in 9.76 days which is in between Controlled Platinum F1 and Platinum F1:250 ppm i.e., 9.47 days. D50 at Dalila:250 ppm and Platinum F1:750 ppm were statistically similar which was 9.10 and 9.15 days respectively. On Dalila:500ppm interaction, D50 was found to be 8.61 days.

Table 4: Days to 50 % emergence of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022

Treatment	D50
Hormone	
Control	9.91 ^c
250 ppm	9.29 ^b
500 ppm	8.34 ^a
750 ppm	8.45 ^a
SEm (±)	0.01785
LSD(α=0.05)	0.21661
CV	1.94%
F test(α=0.05)	6.323e-10***

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Variety	
Dalila	8.81 ^a
Platinum F1	9.19 ^b
SEm (\pm)	0.02525
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	0.15317
CV	1.94%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.0001109***
Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	9.76 ^{ef}
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	10.06 ^f
Dalila @ 250 ppm	9.10 ^d
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	9.47 ^e
Dalila @ 500 ppm	8.61 ^c
Platinum @ 500 ppm	8.06 ^b
Dalila @ 750 ppm	7.75 ^a
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	9.15 ^d
SEm (\pm)	0.01262
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	0.30634
CV	1.94%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	1.900e-06***
Grand Mean	8.99

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

Total no. of seedling germination (Germination %)

Table 5: Total no. of seedling germination of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	Germination
Hormone	
Control	64.83 ^c
250 ppm	75.00 ^b
500 ppm	83.17 ^a
750 ppm	83.17 ^a
SEm (\pm)	1.458881
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	4.425058
CV	4.668717%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	8.37e-07 ***
Variety	
Dalila	79.42 ^a
Platinum F1	73.67 ^b
SEm (\pm)	1.031585
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	3.128988
CV	4.668717%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.001476 **
Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	
Dalila @ 250 ppm	
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	
Dalila @ 500 ppm	

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Platinum @ 500 ppm	
Dalila @ 750 ppm	
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	
SEm (\pm)	
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	
CV	
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	ns
Grand Mean	76.54

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

The total number of seedling germination was influenced by both Hormone concentration and varietal difference. The interaction between the two was non-significant. The highest no. of seedling germination was found on both 500 and 750 ppm concentrations which was 83.17 per plot for both followed by 250 ppm where germination % was 75 and the lowest germination was resulted by control treatment which was 64.83 seedlings per plot. Similarly, Dalila was superior with 79.41 no. of seedling emergence per plot to the Platinum F1 variety which had an average germination of 73.67 per 100 seeds

Height at Transplanting

Table 6: Height at transplantation of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	Height at Transplanting (cm)
Hormone	
Control	10.01 ^c
250 ppm	11.80 ^b
500 ppm	13.97 ^a
750 ppm	14.35 ^a
SEm (\pm)	0.2074
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	0.6291
CV	4.054%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	1.504e-09***
Variety	
Dalila	12.88 ^a
Platinum F1	12.18 ^b
SEm (\pm)	0.1467
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	0.4448
CV	4.054%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.004319**
Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	10.27 ^e
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	9.75 ^e
Dalila @ 250 ppm	11.27 ^d
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	12.33 ^c
Dalila @ 500 ppm	13.67 ^b
Platinum @ 500 ppm	14.27 ^b
Dalila @ 750 ppm	16.33 ^a

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PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	12.37 ^c
SEm (\pm)	0.2933
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	0.8897
CV	4.054%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	2.337e-06***
Grand Mean	12.53 cm

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

Height at transplantation was significantly influenced by Hormonal dose, Varietal difference and Interaction between these two. The average height at 750 and 500 ppm concentration was 14.35 and 13.97 cm which were statistically the same. Followed by 11.8 cm at 250 ppm. The lowest height of 10.01 cm was the result of control treatment. The Dalila variety was superior with an average height of 12.88 cm to the Platinum variety whose average height at transplanting was 12.18 cm.

Dalila variety at 750 ppm had highest average height at transplanting i.e., 16.33cm followed by both varieties at 500 ppm which was 14.27 and 13.67 cm for Platinum and Dalila respectively. Average heights of Platinum at 250 and 750 ppm were statistically similar which were 12.33 cm and 12.37 cm respectively. Controlled treatment of both varieties resulted in the statistically lowest height which was 10.27 and 9.75 cm for Dalila and Platinum F1 respectively.

Height at 15 Days after transplanting

Height at 15 DAT was influenced significantly by hormone and variety as well as their interactions. The average height was superior at 500 and 750 ppm which was 33.78 and 34.58 cm respectively which were statistically similar, followed by 27.07 cm at 250 ppm. The height was least at control treatment which was 22.32 cm. Likewise, the average height at 15 DAT was significantly higher for the Dalila variety i.e., 30.68 cm as compared to 28.19 cm for Platinum F1.

Dalila variety at 750 ppm had the highest average height at 15 days after i.e., 40.77 cm followed by both varieties at 500 ppm which were 34.33 and 33.23 cm for Platinum and Dalila respectively. Average heights of Platinum at 250 and 750 ppm as well as Dalila at 250 ppm were statistically similar which were 28.47, 28.40 and 25.67 cm respectively. Controlled treatment of both varieties resulted in the statistically lowest height which was 23.07 and 21.57 cm for Dalila and Platinum F1 respectively.

Table 7: Height at 15 Days after transplanting of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	Height @15DAT
Hormone	
Control	22.32 ^c
250 ppm	27.07 ^b
500 ppm	33.78 ^a
750 ppm	34.58 ^a
SEm (\pm)	0.8486
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	2.5740
CV	7.061%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	1.464e-07***

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Variety	
Dalila	30.68 ^a
Platinum F1	28.19 ^b
SEm (\pm)	0.60
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	1.82
CV	7.061%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.01084*
Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	23.07 ^{de}
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	21.57 ^c
Dalila @ 250 ppm	25.67 ^{cd}
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	28.47 ^c
Dalila @ 500 ppm	33.23 ^b
Platinum @ 500 ppm	34.33 ^b
Dalila @ 750 ppm	40.77 ^a
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	28.40 ^c
SEm (\pm)	1.20
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	3.64
CV	7.061%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	8.063e-05***
Grand Mean	29.44cm

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test)

Plant Height at 30 days after transplantation

Height at 30 DAT was influenced significantly by hormone and variety as well as their interactions. The average height was superior at 500 and 750 ppm which was 75.17 and 76.67 cm respectively which were statistically similar, followed by 65.67cm at 250 ppm. The height was the least at the control treatment which was 52.67 cm. Likewise, the average height at 30 DAT was significantly higher for the Dalila variety i.e., 69.83 cm as compared to 65.25 cm for Platinum F1.

Dalila variety at 750 ppm had the highest average height at 30 days after transplanting i.e., 86.67 cm followed by both varieties at 500 ppm which were 76.33 and 74.00 cm for Platinum and Dalila respectively. Average heights of Platinum at 250 and 750 ppm as well as Dalila at 250 ppm were statistically similar which were 66.67, 66.67 and 64.67 cm respectively. Controlled treatment of both varieties resulted in the statistically lowest average height which was 54.00 and 51.33 cm for Dalila and Platinum F1 respectively.

Table 8: Height at 30 Days after transplanting of tomato plants influenced by using different dose of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	Height @ 30 DAT
Hormone	
Control	52.67 ^c
250 ppm	65.67 ^b
500 ppm	75.17 ^a
750 ppm	76.67 ^a
SEm (\pm)	1.984

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LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	6.021
CV	7.199%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	1.947e-06***
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Variety	
Dalila	69.83 ^a
Platinum F1	65.25 ^b
<hr/>	
SEm (\pm)	1.404
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	4.257
CV	7.199%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.036704*
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Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	54.00 ^e
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	51.33 ^e
Dalila @ 250 ppm	64.67 ^d
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	66.67 ^{cd}
Dalila @ 500 ppm	74.00 ^{bc}
Platinum @ 500 ppm	76.33 ^b
Dalila @ 750 ppm	86.67 ^a
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	66.67 ^{cd}
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SEm (\pm)	2.807
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	8.515
CV	7.199%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.004068**
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Grand Mean	67.54 cm

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

Plant Height at 45 days after transplantation

Table 9: Height at 45 Days after transplanting of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	Height @ 45 DAT
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Hormone	
Control	98.67 ^c
250 ppm	122.0 ^b
500 ppm	142.0 ^a
750 ppm	143.5 ^a
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SEm (\pm)	3.7363
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	11.333
CV	7.232%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	1.722e-06***
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Variety	
Dalila	131.25 ^a
Platinum F1	121.83 ^b
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SEm (\pm)	2.642
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	8.0135
CV	7.232%

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F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.024483*
Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	101.33 ^e
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	96.00 ^e
Dalila @ 250 ppm	120.67 ^d
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	123.33 ^d
Dalila @ 500 ppm	141.33 ^{bc}
Platinum @ 500 ppm	142.67 ^b
Dalila @ 750 ppm	161.67 ^a
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	125.33 ^{cd}
SEm (+)	5.284
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	16.03
CV	7.232%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.007634**
Grand Mean	126.542 cm

Note: SEM: Standard error of mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

The plant height when measured at 45 days after transplanting found to be influenced by Hormonal, Varietal as well as interaction between the two. The average height was highest at 750 ppm i.e., 143.5cm which is significantly indifferent to 142cm at 500ppm followed by 122cm at 250 ppm. The lowest average height of 98.67cm was the result of control treatment. Dalila variety with an average height of 131.25cm was significantly superior to Platinum F1 with an average height of 121.83cm.

The interaction between variety and hormones also influenced the average plant height at 45 DAT. Dalila at 750 ppm has resulted in a maximum height of 161.67cm followed by Platinum F1 and Dalila at 500 ppm with an average height of 142.67cm and 141.33 cm respectively. Platinum F1 at 750 ppm, Dalila at 250 ppm and Platinum F1 at 250 ppm resulted in significantly indifferent average heights of 125.33 cm, 120.67cm and 123.33 cm respectively. The lowest height resulted by controlled treatment on both varieties with 96 cm and 101.33 cm height respectively for Platinum F1 and Dalila varieties.

Flowering

Only the varietal difference influenced the average flower numbers per plant. The variation caused by hormonal differences and interaction between the two was not significantly different at a 5% level of significance. At both 30 and 45 days after transplanting the Dalila variety was superior with an average number of 5.50 and 11.67 flowers per plant at 30 and 45 days after transplanting. Whereas Platinum F1 had an average number of 4.25 and 9.50 flowers per plant at 30 and 45 days after transplanting respectively.

Table 10: Flowering at 30 and 45 Days after transplanting of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	No. of Flowers/Plant @30DAT	No. of Flowers/Plant @45 DAT
Hormone		
Control		
250 ppm		
500 ppm		
750 ppm		

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SEm (\pm)		
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)		
CV		
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	NS	NS
Variety		
Dalila	5.50 ^a	11.67 ^a
Platinum F1	4.25 ^b	9.50 ^b
SEm (\pm)	0.370011	0.555008
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	1.122313	1.683441
CV	26.29244%	18.16632%
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.03154*	0.01533*
Hormone: Variety		
Dalila @ 0ppm		
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm		
Dalila @ 250 ppm		
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm		
Dalila @ 500 ppm		
Platinum @ 500 ppm		
Dalila @ 750 ppm		
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm		
SEm (\pm)		
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)		
CV		
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	NS	NS
Grand Mean	4.88	10.58

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

Fruiting

Table 11: Flowering at 30 and 45 Days after transplanting of tomato plants influenced by using different doses of GA3 on different varieties at Siddhalek, Dhading, Nepal, 2022.

Treatment	No. of Flowers/Plant @45 DAT
Hormone	
Control	
250 ppm	
500 ppm	
750 ppm	
SEm (\pm)	
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	
CV	
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	NS
Variety	
Dalila	5.42 ^a
Platinum F1	3.92 ^b
SEm (\pm)	0.447
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	1.356

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CV	33.19
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	0.03255*
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Hormone: Variety	
Dalila @ 0ppm	
PlatinumF1 @ 0 ppm	
Dalila @ 250 ppm	
PlatinumF1 @ 250 ppm	
Dalila @ 500 ppm	
Platinum @ 500 ppm	
Dalila @ 750 ppm	
PlatinumF1 @ 750 ppm	
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SEm (\pm)	
LSD($\alpha=0.05$)	
CV	
F test($\alpha=0.05$)	NS
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Grand Mean	4.67

Note: SEM: Standard error of the mean, LSD: Least significant difference, CV: Coefficient of variation, ns: non-significant, ***: Significant at 0.1% probability level, **: Significant at 1% probability level, *: Significant at 5% probability level, values with the same letters in the columns are not significantly different at 5% DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test).

Fruiting was quantified by taking the average number of fruits per plant. When measured at 45 days after transplanting it was found that only varietal difference caused significantly different variation. Dalila was superior to Platinum F1 with an average fruit number of 5.42 per plant whereas later had only 3.92 fruits per plant on average when measured at the same time.

DISCUSSIONS

Gibberellins act in the mobilization of seed reserves during the germination process. Therefore, they are considered important germination promoters and contribute to increased seed germination speed and uniformity thus improving the performance (Zanotti et al., 2014). The promising effect of GA₃ as a pre-sowing treatment for the seeds replaced the dormancy mechanism of the seeds resulting in early germination (Khan, 1981). Gibberellins (GAs) contribute to the expression of certain genes related to germination in tomatoes (Davies, 2004). Application of GA₃@ 500 ppm for 24 h has ensured early germination with an increase in seed germination. This treatment also improved the seedling growth with an increase in root formation and vigour index (Singh & Kaur, 2020). Gibberellic acid is responsible for stimulating the production of mRNA molecules in the cells and mRNA produced in this form, codes for the hydrolytic enzymes, which in turn improves the chance of fast growth (Sun, 2004). In contrast with the result of (Islam et al., 2006) who found that GA₃ at 100 mg/L (100 ppm) produced the highest shoot length as in this research GA₃ at 500 and 750 ppm have shown the best effects. Similarly, (López & Hernandez, 2009) reported that soaking tomato seeds in 900 mg·L⁻¹ GA₃ resulted in the highest germination percentage, root length, dry matter, stem and root fresh matter and leaf area, while the fastest average sprouting rate and tallest height were due to 300 mg·L⁻¹ GA₃ treatment and with 900 mg·L⁻¹ GA₃ allows obtaining more vigorous tomato seedlings in less time and with a better development in field. This suggests that different types of seeds and distinct genotypes require specific doses of GA₃ for the most efficient results. In contrast to (Gurudev & Saxena, 1991) who reported gibberellin increases the flowering and fruit set, in our research the characters in the later stage of the plant life (Flowering and fruiting) didn't show a significant difference concerning treated GA₃ concentration.

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that the seed treatment of GA3 has a significant and positive influence on the pre and post-transplanting characteristics of the tomato plant. GA3 doses at 500 ppm and 750 ppm have shown the best effect. The Dalila variety was superior to Platinum in treated as well as control plots. The Dalila:750 ppm interaction and Platinum:500 ppm interaction was significantly superior to other interactions for respective varieties. At 750 ppm, the performance of Platinum F1 was reduced as compared to the same variety at 500 ppm. So, we can conclude that the higher dose of hormone has adverse effects too. In later stages, the hormone had no significant impact and only the varieties created significant variance among which Dalila was found to be superior.

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